

Integrated Parasite Management for Controlling Livestock Parasites

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Introduction

Livestock is the bone of Indian economy and an essential integral part of everyday life and contributes for 4.11% GDP and almost 25.6% to the total Agriculture GDP. Any lacking in livestock exaggerating its health, depreciating its value and productivity which in turn become a constrain in growing the Indian economy with the internal parasite being the most economically important constrain standing beforehand. Parasitic infections has huge economic significance, tends to be more chronic and take a sharp toll to the the point of anorectic, lethargic, unthriftiness, unproductive and death before the parasite can even be presented. which have been demonstrated repeatedly and losses due to gastrointestinal (GI) nematodes is considerable, of which *Ostertagia ostertagia* and *Cooperia* spp. being the most important GI nematodes of ruminants and a mixture of these infections normally occur under typical farm conditions.

Control of these parasites based on a single method of control has been found to be almost impossible and non-sustainable in the long-term condition. Therefore, multi-directional and multi-label approaches has become obvious for controlling parasites which are practically and ecologically sustainable in long run. So the concept of management techniques and treatment together has been put on effort as a solution to the effect of parasitism over the livestock. This term is singly called as "Integrated Parasite Management". The IPM has gained much concern once it is found that parasites are becoming complete resistant against almost all classes of dewormers. The "Integrated Parasite Management" is the integration of management and treatment in multiple ways which works parallelly and co-ordinate in all the suitable and possible ways considering in views of social, economic and environmental aspects. Integrated control sought to identify the best admixture of chemical and biological controls for a given insect pest.

History

IPM was formulated into national policy in February 1972 when President Richard Nixon directed federal agencies to take steps to advance the application of IPM in all relevant sectors. In 1979, President Jimmy Carter established an —Interagency IPM Coordinating Committee to ensure development and implementation of IPM practices. In 1997, Perry Adkison and Ray. F. Smith received World Food Nobel Prize for encouraging the use of IPM

Control measures can be broadly done by:

1) Chemical Control

Treatment with drugs: This is the most dominant way in controlling the parasitism, they are so formulated and their dose are so designed that will kill or expel the parasite without contributing any harmful effects to the animal productivity. So, dose of the drug after accessing the correct diagnosis and actual body weight is important and should be taken very carefully because underdose and overdose will lead to drug resistance. More often, drugs should be used only if prescribed by the concern veterinary doctor. Same kind of drugs should not be used for ages. Classes of anthelmintics should be changed after a certain period of time. FECR should be checked after every anthelmintic use and if found less i.e., (FECR < 90) should be immediately stopped. The strategic treatment should be done based on weather condition and geographical distribution. To minimize the marginal effectiveness always give supportive therapy like Vitamins B12, iron source, electrolytes, probiotics, protein rich diet.

Sometime we should give treatment to the half population leaving some animals untreated which is popularly known as **worm refugia**. The untreated group will dilute the resistant gene which in turn prolongs the anthelmintic use. Refugium has been identified as a crucial component in prolonging the use of anthelmintic actions.

Natural dewormer. Instead, we can use some herbal dewormer like seeds or foliage of plant such as garlic, onion, mint, walnuts, dill, parsley, cucumber, pumpkin and wormwood, Charcoal, Wild ginger or snakeroot, Conifers (pine, spruce, fir), Mustard and castor oil, Squash or pumpkin seeds, Carrot and fennel seeds, Pyrethrum (plant extract from Chrysanthemum). Cucumber and pumpkin seeds helped the tapeworms to be expelled from the GIT: Oil of chenopodium is used to treat parasitic infection including humans.

Target selective treatment (TST): It is an idea of treating animals in need of such a treatment and only them i.e., on individual basis. The animal is detected directly by estimating the parasite load. FAMACHA, DAG score and Body condition score (BCS) are the most frequently used techniques.

TST is regarded as a comprehensive and aggregated tool in the integrated parasite management. The most on-farm proven method is the FAMACHA which evaluates the clinical anaemia. Candidates for TST are nasal discharge (for nasal bots), paling of ocular mucous membranes for anaemia (for haematophagous worms), submandibular oedema or

Level of anaemia			
Clinical category	Color	PCV (%)	Treatment
1	Red	>28	No
2	Red-pink	23-27	No
3	Pink	18-22	?
4	Pink-white	13-17	Yes
5	White	<12	Yes

bottle jaw (for haematophagous worms and conical fluke). FAMACHA is based on mucus membrane coloration catagorised from (1-5) depending upon the level of anaemia.

Always use the paler score: not half score. The card can be replaced at time if necessary.

Dag Score: Dag is defined as faecal contamination of the wool or hair coat around the tail and hindquarters which is the result of gastrointestinal parasitism. A dag score gives an approximation of faecal consistency or prevalence of diarrhoea in the group of animals especially for the ovines and caprines. The more the Dagginess or fecal soiling is, the more the chance to be associated with fly strike. It is recommended that dag score is recorded twice to improve accuracy of the trait. First score soon after weaning (3/4 months) & Second score – 8 months

Score 5, very daggy, consider culling the sheep prior to mating.

We should also determine the Body condition: by feeling the amount of fat or muscle; rough or smooth which access the parasitic infestation or infection. Eg., Bottle jaw: we should check if any fluid accumulation present in the sub-mandibular region which is the major concern for parasites like *Amphistomes*, *Fasciola*, *Haemonchus*; Nose: Nasal discharge for nasal bots

Biological control

Mites: *Phytoseiid* spp. are capable of consuming *Ascaris* ova in the soil. *Macrocheles muscae domesticae* can eat up to 10 housefly eggs per day. Dragonflies' larvae and nymphs feed on mosquito larvae. Bacteria, Virus, fungi also potentially contribute in parasitic control.

Fishes Mosquito larvae may be controlled by predatory fish like *Gambusia affinis*, *Guppy poecilia* and carp fishes. Introducing *Gambusia affinis* into water wells resulted in 98% reduction in the larval density of *Anopheles stephensi*

Birds: Pick off ticks from the host during flight and also eat the larvae of dung flies. Domestic fowls and birds like duck are predators of snails i.e., intermediate host of trematodes.

Immunological Control:

Vaccination: Vaccines are the utmost important tool in controlling any parasite. Till date some promising targets vaccines are – Barbervax for *Haemonchus*, Tick-GARD and Gavac vaccine against *Rhipicephalus (Boophilus) microplus*. Leishmune against leishmaniosis, S48 strain against abortion in sheep due to primary *Toxoplasma gondii*, Rakshavac-T against *Theileria annulata*, Pirodog against *Babesia canis*

2) Non-Chemical method:

Management: Animal shed must be well ventilated and lighted to maintain required humidity and air circulation (Madke *et al.* 2010). Water should be clean and free from faecal matter. Watering areas should be situated in well drained places with gravel or even cemented floors. Always keep the manure by making heaps so that eggs, larvae, cysts or other stages of parasites are killed due to the heat generated during composting. Newly introduced animals should be quarantined for 4–6 weeks

Nutrition: Well fed animals are always less prone to diseases. Focus should be always on the protein availability and balanced mineral supply. A newly emerged product is copper oxide wire particles to young lambs which reduces settling of abomasal nematodes (*H. contortus* and *O. circumcincta*). They lodged in the abomasal mucosa with a resultant persistent effect against those species susceptible to copper, available in 25 g boluses (Copasure; Animax Veterinary Technology, UK). They slowly release and poorly absorbed from the gut thus there is no copper toxicity. It has been found with high efficacy of COWP against *H. contortus*, particularly in young animals. Mineral Phosphorus showed that when given at 0.28% on dry matter basis aids weight gain by 40% to the parasitic infected animals over phosphorus given at low 0.18%.

By pass protein: Stear *et al.*, have found that increasing bypass protein (not degraded in rumen) helps in protecting the animal from weight loss. Fish meal is a great source of bypass protein which results

in an increase in the concentration of mast cell proteinases and elevation in levels of circulating eosinophils. Plants containing condensed tannins have also bypass protein and in turn have anthelmintic properties. Animals grazing tannin rich forages have lower faecal egg counts.

Pasture management: Proper observation of the animal and understanding the interaction between the host, parasite and the soil will keep the animal away from the parasite. Most of the worm larvae crawl only a few inches up onto the plants. Sheep eat much lower to the ground than cattle do, picking up large numbers of larvae. Therefore, it is important to monitor sheep closely so they don't graze too low. Larva usually migrate very close to the manure pile, if animals are not allowed to graze around their own manure pile can reduce larvae intake. The three most important things i.e., warmth, oxygen and moisture enhance the survival of larvae on pasture. Good grazing management, that may be clean grazing (not being grazed for more than 12 months share less parasites) or, pasture that has been hayed, renovated, or rotated with row crops.

Conclusion

Any unthrifty or thin animal with a rough hair coat or diarrhea is not necessarily wormy. This condition may be due to climate change, feed shortage, stress etc., so one must check worms or its eggs or larvae in the faecal culture for the confirmation. Every control measure has its pros and cons. General way to defeat the parasitism is good treatment by proper diagnosis and well-tolerated anthelmintics having broad spectrum activity along with good managerial practices considerably lowers the chance of parasitic infection.

